

THERMODYNAMIC ASSESSMENT OF *SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE* CATALYZED FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP JUICE

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ABSTRACT

The rate of Soursop fermentation with *saccharomyces cerevisiae* was studied at temperatures between 30° and 42°C in order to characterize the process using thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy (ΔH^*), activation energy (ΔE^*), entropy (ΔS^*), Gibbs free energy (ΔG^*) and equilibrium constant (K). The parameters were evaluated on the basis of a consideration of Arrhenius, Eyring and van't Hoff's equations. The results obtained are ΔH^* , 151.148 KJmol⁻¹; ΔE^* , 151.148 KJmol⁻¹, ΔS^* , 275.35Jmol⁻¹K⁻¹; ΔG^* , -752.213 KJmol⁻¹, and equilibrium constant, K, 1.33 dm³mol⁻¹. These values were subsequently used to obtain the rate constant of the fermentation k, 1.42x10²⁴ min⁻¹, Arrhenius constant A (pre-exponential or frequency factor), 1.51 x10²³ min⁻¹; orientation parameter, P, 1.41x10⁻³⁴ and the collision frequency Z, 1.07x10¹¹ min⁻¹. The calculated fermentation efficiency is 382.84% for soursop. The results showed that though the fermentation process is kinetically controlled, it is suggested that the positive impact of the feasible thermodynamics is limited by other process variables.

INTRODUCTION

The thermodynamic assessment of an enzyme catalyzed fermentation process provides a key instrument for efficiently controlling fermentation based reactions (Russel, 2002, Chang, 2005). This however requires a thorough understanding of the application of basic laws of thermodynamics especially in scale up processes. However, models that will all-time be applicable to all possible substrate and catalysts are yet to be provided (Haq et al., 2010, Duy and Fitter, 2005). Such model will take into account the spontaneity of the fermentation, the nature of the substrate, the sugar content (glucose etc.), extent and direction of fermentation, the driving force, the catalyst (enzymes), the nature of the intermediate and products such as alcohol, aldehydes, kinetics etc. and the inhibitory factors and possibilities (Eisenthal et al., 2007). A continuous search for possible models to account for enzyme catalyzed reactions, a step by step but steady approach will assist in accumulating the necessary data towards achieving the aim (Negi and Anand, 2007). Arrhenius, Eyring and van't Hoff's models were deployed to characterize the fermentation of soursop juice using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. It is hoped that this work will be able to establish quantitatively some process variables as they relate to each other.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Soursop fruit was purchased from Iruekpen market, Esan West L.G.A. Edo State, Nigeria. pH meter -pocket-sized, Hanna product, was standardized with appropriate buffer solution of pH 4. Yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*), supplied by Vahine professional, Mc cormick, France SAS was used as received.

PREPARATION OF SOURSOP JUICE

The soursop fruit was washed with distilled water and then peeled with hand. The juice was manually squeezed out with a muslin cloth and preserved.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fermentation vessels were sterilized with a 3% solution of sodium metabisulphite for 5 minutes. A litre (1000cm³) of juice was properly conditioned by sterilizing at 90°C and was brought to the required pH with either 0.1MHCl or 0.1MNaOH. Seven fermentors containing substrate were prepared for each of seven sampling times at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, and 210 (min). The sample was fermented in the sealed polymeric fermentors with connected tubes for the estimation of gas production. Yeast (1g) was added to each of the fermentor. The substrate and the yeast were properly mixed by shaking and the yeast allowed to activate for 20minutes. The escape of CO₂ was prevented by sealing the air inlet with a cresol-perfumed jelly.

The CO₂ produced in each sealed fermentor was collected in water and measured, by titrating with 0.1M NaOH using phenolphthalein indicator. The rate of fermentation was measured as the volume of CO₂ produced at 30 minute intervals of time. The effect of temperature on fermentation was determined by keeping other factors such as substrate concentration, pH of the juice, yeast concentration, and fermentation time constant. The temperature was varied between 30 - 42°C, using a thermostated water bath. In determining the effect of substrate concentration on fermentation, all other factors such as temperature, pH, yeast concentration, and fermentation time were kept constant. The substrate concentration was varied between 20 – 80% (v/v). In determining the effect of pH on fermentation, factors like substrate concentration, temperature, fermentation time and yeast concentration were kept constant. The pH meter was standardized with a buffer 4 solution. The pH was varied by the introduction of 0.1M H₂SO₄ or 0.1M NaOH solution to the required pH value and measured by a pH meter. The pH of the juice was varied between 3.0-6.0 (pH). The effect of yeast concentration on fermentation was determined by varying yeast concentration between 1-7% (w/v).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: DATA ON THE RATE OF FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP SUGAR CATALYZED BY *SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE* AT pH 5.0 AND 1.0% YEAST CONCENTRATION (W/V) AT VARIOUS SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATIONS AND TEMPERATURES.

Substrate concentration	Rate of Fermentation						
	Temperature/°C						
	30	32	34	36	38	40	42
20	0.538	0.535	0.551	0.666	0.656	0.708	0.626
30	0.531	0.685	0.665	0.582	0.636	0.558	0.634
40	0.589	0.660	0.702	0.667	0.558	0.641	0.696
50	0.553	0.807	0.644	0.702	0.582	0.586	0.769
60	0.556	0.659	0.702	0.611	0.666	0.575	0.727
70	0.697	0.734	0.702	0.531	0.596	0.679	0.520
80	0.867	0.483	0.636	0.556	0.556	0.566	0.558

Table 2: DATA ON THE ln-RATE OF FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP SUGAR CATALYZED BY *SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE* AT pH 5.0 AND 1.0 % YEAST CONCENTRATION (W/V) AT VARIOUS ln-SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATIONS AND TEMPERATURES.

In-substrate concentration	In- Rate of Fermentation						
	Temperature /°C						
	30	32	34	36	38	40	42
2.995	-0.619	-0.625	-0.596	-0.401	-0.421	-0.345	-0.468
3.401	-0.632	-0.378	-0.407	-0.541	-0.452	-0.583	-0.455
3.688	-0.529	-0.415	-0.353	-0.404	-0.583	-0.444	-0.362
3.912	-0.529	-0.214	-0.441	-0.353	-0.541	-0.534	-0.262
4.094	-0.586	-0.417	-0.353	-0.492	-0.406	-0.553	-0.318
4.248	-0.360	-0.309	-0.353	-0.632	-0.517	-0.387	-0.653
4.382	-0.142	-0.727	-0.452	-0.586	-0.586	-0.569	-0.583

Fig 1. VARIATION OF RATE OF FERMENTATION WITH SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES (pH 5.0; 1.0% YEAST CONCENTRATION W/V)

TABLE 3: DATA FROM RECIPROCAL OF TEMPERATURE AND lnk FROM ln-RATE AND ln-SUBSTRATE PLOT

$T(^{\circ}C)$	30	32	34	36	38	40	42
$T(K)$	303	305	307	309	311	313	315
$1/T$	0.00330	0.00328	0.00326	0.00324	0.00322	0.00320	0.00318
$1/T \cdot 10^{-3}$	3.30	3.28	3.26	3.24	3.22	3.20	3.18
lnk	-1.507	-0.559	-0.836	-0.051	-0.217	-0.203	-0.173

Fig.2: PLOT OF lnk VERSUS 1/T FOR THE SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE CATALYZED FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP SUGAR

Table 4: THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS CALCULATED FOR THE SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE CATALYZED FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP SUGAR.

<i>Thermodynamic parameter</i>	<i>Values</i>
Enthalpy ΔH^* (kJmol^{-1})	151.148
Activation Energy E_a^* (kJmol^{-1})	151.148
Entropy ΔS^* ($\text{Jmol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	275.359
Gibbs Energy ΔG^* (kJmol^{-1})	-752.213
Equilibrium constant (K_{eq})	1.33

Table 5: CALCULATED CONSTANTS FOR THE SACCHAROMYCES CEREVISIAE CATALYZED FERMENTATION OF SOURSOP SUGAR

Rate constant (k)	1.42×10^{24}
A (min^{-1})	1.51×10^{23}
P	1.41×10^{-34}
Z (min^{-1})	1.07×10^{11}

The thermodynamic parameters ΔH^* , ΔE_a^* , ΔS^* , ΔG^* and K , were obtained from a plot of $\ln k$ versus $1/T$ (Figure 2) on the basis of Eyring's equation. The results show that the enthalpy value is positive indicating that the fermentation process is endothermic while the calculated value for the activation energy is same as the enthalpy. The entropy value is positive corroborating the positive enthalpy value. The fermentation process is spontaneous as shown by the negative change in free energy. The equilibrium constant indicates that the conversion of substrate to products is 33% for soursop. Table 5 shows the calculated value for k (rate constant), A (pre-exponential or frequency factor) and P (orientation parameter). The above results support the proposed two step mechanism of the enzyme catalyzed reaction. The enzyme-substrate complex is simply a non-isolable intermediate which though is an energized molecule is thus present in low concentration and hence, the first step which is the equilibrium step is quantified by the Eyring and van't Hoff's isotherms while the second or decomposition step is adequately quantified by a combination of the Arrhenius, Eyring and van't Hoff's isotherms. The data shown in Table 5 is within the range of data obtained by biochemical microcalorimetry for glucose sugar (Chang, 1990). The calculated A and the P values obtained on the basis of collision theory and absolute reaction rate theory (or transition state theory), respectively show that the collision factor is of the order of 10^{11} min^{-1} , about half that of gaseous molecules that can only be attained by an induced reduction in activation energy by a catalyst. The frequency factor A , in the Arrhenius equation is approximately equal to $K_B T/h e^{\Delta S^*/R}$ of the absolute reaction rate theory and the van't Hoff's equation. However, in doing so, the thermodynamics is suggestively limited by other process variables such as concentration of the substrate, the purity and activity of the enzyme molecules as well as product inhibition (Riaz et al., 2007; Tanaka and Hoshino, 2003). This fact, invariably, influenced the yield of product in practice. The enzyme provides a favourable kinetic environment for submicroscopic interactions of the enzyme-substrate complex

and such interaction could be substrate interacting more with the complex or rather, the product interacting more with the intermediate complex. The equilibrium constant value K suggests that the intermediate complex is rather interacting more with the substrate and also showing that only a limited amount of the substrate is converted to product. The fraction of effective intermolecular collision increases with increase in the total number of collisions and hence the rate of reaction is proportional to the collision frequency as seen in Table 5. The P (orientation factor) value affects the interaction between substrate and enzyme. The enzyme activates the substrate molecules at particular active sites. These sites have definite size and shape or configuration. A reaction will proceed only if the size, stereochemistry and orientation of the substrate molecules fit into the active sites of the enzyme. The value of P in Table 5 show that the orientation of molecules affects the probability factor and that simple molecule indeed have more ways of proper orientation to form complex intermediates. Hence, the probability factor is of the order applicable for simple molecules (Malinowski, 2001; Pisarenko et al., 2001). For simple sugars like glucose, the orientation factor is expected to be large and hence the P value obtained in Table 5. The equilibrium constant K is observed to be $1.33 \text{ (dm}^3\text{mol}^{-1}\text{)}$ and not significantly far from unity implying that ΔG^* can be conveniently equated with the change in free energy at standard conditions. The equilibrium constant value support the fact that the unstable intermediate as in this case is interacting more with the substrate and in such a given situation, the yield of product should not be expected to be large. This explains partly why the yield of alcohol from most fermentable starches and sugars are low. It is of interest frequently to estimate the efficiency of a fermentation process (Chang, 1990; Leksawasdi et al., 2001) by a consideration of the free energy of combustion of glucose: $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{6(s)} + 6\text{O}_{2(g)} \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_{2(g)} + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)}$ $\Delta G^* = -2879 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$. On the other hand, the fermentation of sugar syrup to alcohol as summarized by the equation,

$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{6(s)} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO}_{2(g)} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}_{(l)}$, in this investigation gave $\Delta G^* = -752 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$. Therefore, the calculated fermentation efficiency is 382.84%. The high efficiency of the process is suggested to be promoted by the P value and a suitable kinetics.

CONCLUSION

The cross plots of yeast and substrate concentration have shown that at maximum rate 1%(w/v) yeast is required to ferment 27%(v/v) substrate (soursop) while at half maximum rate, 2%(w/v) yeast is required to ferment 45%(v/v) substrate of soursop.

RECOMMENDATION

The findings of this work recommend that alcohol production by fermentation of soursop using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* should be conducted at optimum conditions of temperature 32-36°C; pH 5.0-5.5; substrate concentration 50%(v/v), and yeast concentration 3.5-4.5%(w/v). The work also recommends that 2%(w/v) yeast is required to ferment 45%(v/v) substrate of soursop at half maximum rate.

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